

DigiScope-E2O

A Multilevel Framework for the Analysis of Digital Competence Training Programmes in Second Chance Schools

A methodology for understanding, analysing,
and improving digital education from
a comprehensive and contextualised perspective.

ORIENTA-DIG R&D&I Project

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Methodological report

“DigiScope-E2O. A multi-level tool for the analysis of digital skills training programmes in Second Chance Schools”.

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Introduction

The increasing digitalisation of social, educational and working life has made digital skills one of the essential capabilities for full participation and the exercise of rights in society (CEDEFOP, 2021). Currently, much of our training, access to information, use of public services, job search and social interaction takes place in technology-mediated environments. Consequently, access to these resources and the ability to benefit from the opportunities they offer depend, to a large extent, on people's ability to navigate such environments.

From this perspective, digitalisation cannot be understood as a neutral or automatically inclusive process. Technologies can serve both as a means of reducing inequalities and as a mechanism that contributes to reinforcing them when the necessary conditions are not in place. This reality poses significant challenges for disadvantaged groups, and in particular for young people in vulnerable situations, as the difficulties they face in participating digitally are often part of broader contexts of exclusion (Pawluczuk, 2020).

The potential of technology to address this complexity depends not only on its characteristics or on young people's individual skills, but also on the opportunities created to support their development (Stevens et al., 2017). In this regard, guidance and training play an important role in providing personalised support that addresses the specific needs, circumstances and pathways of each young person.

A clear example of personalised support is provided by Second Chance Schools (E2O), where the development of digital skills is integrated into educational, personal and socio-occupational support processes for young people in disadvantaged situations. However, understanding the contribution of these schools to digital inclusion requires going beyond an analysis of young people's needs or the practices implemented by professionals. It is also necessary to examine how initiatives for the development of digital skills are designed and implemented, and what place they occupy within the organisational strategies of these centres.

It is against this backdrop that **DigiScope-E2O** has emerged: a tool designed to provide an integrated analysis of how Second Chance Schools promote the development of digital skills. Its name combines the term '*digital*' with the notion of '*scope*' (range or breadth of perspective), reflecting the intention to offer a systemic and comprehensive approach that allows this phenomenon to be studied beyond a single dimension of analysis. Rather than focusing exclusively on programme content, the practices carried out by professionals or the organisational conditions of the centres, DigiScope-E2O proposes an integrated analysis of these three levels, recognising that opportunities for digital learning depend on the interaction between them.

To this end, the tool is structured around three grids with complementary dimensions: the curricular dimension, geared towards analysing the digital competences promoted by training activities; the professional dimension, centred on the implementation and support strategies developed by professionals; and the organisational dimension, linked to the institutional conditions that facilitate the planning, integration and sustainability of such initiatives. This perspective will enable us to understand not only which digital competences are promoted in E2Os, but also how they are developed and under what organisational conditions they acquire meaning and continuity.

Why use a multi-level framework for analysing digital skills training programmes?

Training programmes are dynamic processes that take shape through the interaction between different actors, contexts and levels of action. Caley et al. (2021) have pointed out that one of the most common limitations of analyses of educational interventions is a tendency to focus on participants or the results obtained, whilst relegating to the background the implementation processes and organisational contexts that shape their development. The authors note that many analyses pay little attention to factors such as organisational culture, institutional systems or implementation dynamics, despite their influence on how programmes operate. This highlights the need to look beyond individual

learning and

incorporate those contextual elements that help explain how and why certain processes and outcomes occur.

In the field of digital literacy, it has been shown that the learning opportunities generated by programmes depend on multiple factors linked to their design, implementation and organisational context. In this regard, Detlor et al. (2022) highlight the importance of aspects such as the availability of resources, staff training, assessment mechanisms and the characteristics of the organisations implementing these initiatives.

In line with these perspectives, the study of digital skills training programmes developed in E2Os requires an approach capable of capturing this complexity. This involves simultaneously considering the digital skills promoted through the programmes, the practices through which they are implemented and supported by the professionals in charge, and the organisational conditions underpinning their development.

Methodological approach

This research adopts a qualitative approach that seeks to understand how Second Chance Schools promote the development of digital skills from a multi-level perspective. To this end, the training programmes developed by the centres will be analysed, focusing on their content, implementation and the organisational conditions that facilitate their development, based on the following research question.

Research question:

Which digital skills are promoted in the programmes developed by Second Chance Schools, how are they implemented by the professionals in charge, and how are they integrated into the centres' organisational strategies?

General objective:

- To analyse the digital competences promoted by E2Os from a multi-level perspective.

SO1. To characterise the digital competences incorporated into the programmes developed by E2Os, identifying their alignment with European digital competence frameworks.

SO2. To examine how the professionals in charge design, develop and adapt initiatives aimed at developing digital competences among young people in vulnerable situations.

SO3. To identify the organisational elements that underpin the integration of digital competences into E2O strategies, taking into account aspects related to planning, collaboration and institutional resources.

Units of analysis

The DigiScope-E2O application will be developed on the basis of two related units of analysis. The first concerns programmes, projects, teaching materials and other institutional documentation linked to the development of digital competences in schools. The analysis of these documents will enable us to review the programmatic dimension of the proposal, identifying the digital competences developed and the way in which these are integrated into the design of training activities.

The second unit of analysis consists of the discourses and experiences of the stakeholders involved in the design, implementation and coordination of these initiatives. To this end, semi-structured interviews will be conducted with professionals responsible for implementing the programmes and with informants holding organisational responsibilities within the schools. This information will enable a deeper understanding of the professional and organisational dimensions of the framework, providing evidence on the practices developed, the support strategies and the institutional conditions for the development of digital competences. The methodological structure of the study is set out below (Figure 1).

DigComp, DigCompEdu and DigCompOrg for a systemic approach to the study of digital competences in E2O.

Adopting a multi-level perspective for the analysis of training programmes in digital competences requires reference frameworks capable of capturing their complexity. However, none of the European frameworks currently available allows, in isolation, for a simultaneous understanding of the competences promoted through the programmes, the practices developed during their implementation and the necessary organisational conditions.

For this reason, this research combines the DigComp, DigCompEdu and DigCompOrg frameworks in a complementary manner as analytical tools

that

enable a deeper exploration of specific dimensions of the same reality. In this case, DigComp has established itself as the main European benchmark for the conceptualisation of digital competence, defined as the set of knowledge, skills and attitudes necessary to use digital technologies safely, critically, responsibly and effectively in learning, work and social participation (Cosgrove & Cachia, 2025).

The latest update to the framework introduces an explicit structure of learning outcomes that specifies what a person should know, understand or be able to do following a training process, providing a more detailed and practical description of digital competence. Consequently, the curriculum-related dimension of the matrix is based on the five competence areas of DigComp 3.0, enabling an analysis of the correspondence between curriculum content and the digital competences considered a priority in the European context.

The second dimension of analysis is based on DigCompEdu (C & Y, 2017). However, the framework is not used to assess the digital competence of guidance counsellors or educators, as this aspect falls outside the scope of the study. Its inclusion responds, rather, to the need for categories that enable an examination of how digital resources are used, what strategies are employed to integrate technologies into training and support processes, and how these contribute to the development of digital competences among the young participants.

The organisational conditions in which such training takes place have a decisive influence on the learning opportunities available, on the sustainability of the initiatives and on their ability to be integrated into institutional projects. This premise forms the basis of DigCompOrg, a framework developed by the European Commission to understand the integration of digital technologies from an organisational and systemic perspective (P et al., 2015). DigCompOrg conceives of digital transformation as a process involving leadership, governance, professional development, educational practices, collaboration, infrastructure and evaluation mechanisms, recognising the interdependence between these elements.

Given that the purpose of this research is not to assess the degree of digital maturity of organisations, the organisational dimension is not constructed on the basis of the entirety of DigCompOrg, but rather through the areas operationalised in the SELFIE tool, which was developed specifically to translate the framework's principles into observable dimensions of institutional practice. Consequently, the organisational analysis focuses on aspects related to strategic planning, collaboration, infrastructure and institutional support linked to the development of digital competences, taking into account the role these elements play in the development of training programmes.

When considered in a complementary manner, these frameworks provide a conceptual basis for exploring the development of digital competences in greater depth from three interrelated dimensions: the curricular dimension, centred on the competences promoted by the programmes; the professional dimension, aimed at understanding how these skills are implemented through the practices and strategies developed by the professionals in charge; and the organisational dimension, linked to the institutional conditions that either facilitate or hinder their integration within educational institutions. The DigiScope-E2O analysis tool is built on this basis; it is designed for the integrated study of digital competences in E2O at various levels. Figure 2 summarises this proposal and shows the analytical dimensions and questions that structure the research.

Figure 2. DigiScope-E2O analytical framework

DigComp 3.0 indicators

PROGRAMÁTICA

The curricular dimension aims to identify and characterise the digital competences incorporated into training programmes in E2O institutions. To analyse the digital competences promoted by the programmes, this dimension uses the European DigComp 3.0 framework as a reference. However, this framework will not be used to

determining levels of digital competence, but rather as a reference for study that enables the recognition of the presence and focus of the digital competences covered in the programmes.

The analysis will be organised around the five competence areas proposed by DigComp 3.0:

- Information and digital literacy.
- Communication and collaboration.
- Digital content creation.
- Security.
- Problem-solving.

These areas will constitute the main categories of study and will enable us to identify which dimensions of digital competence are promoted by the programmes and which receive greater or lesser attention within the training proposals. Specifically, their presence will be analysed in:

- Learning objectives.
- Expected competences.
- Training content.

- Proposed activities.

- Methodological strategies.
- Resources used.
- Assessment procedures and tools.

This analysis will make it possible to assess not only which digital competences are promoted, but also the extent to which they are integrated into the programme's structure. In this way, it will be possible to distinguish between competences that are formulated in a specific or declarative manner and those that are incorporated across the board into the learning objectives, content, methodologies and activities.

Table 1. Example of an analysis grid for the programme dimension.

DigComp Area	Objective s	Content	Activities	Methodologie s	Assessment
Information and digital literacy					
Communicati on and collaboration					
Content of content					
Safety and wellbeing					
Problem- solving					

DigCompEdu indicators

This second dimension shifts the focus to the practices that take place during the implementation of training programmes. The aim is thus to analyse how the guidelines set out in the programmes translate into concrete learning and support experiences aimed at young people in vulnerable situations.

To this end, the DigCompEdu framework is used as a reference. The selection of its dimensions focuses specifically on those areas linked to the pedagogical development and management of learning experiences mediated by digital technologies. The first category of analysis relates to the area of **digital content**, which in DigCompEdu refers to the selection, creation, adaptation, management and sharing of digital resources used in training processes. Including this category will enable us to examine the types of resources used, the criteria applied and the strategies developed to adapt these materials to the needs and characteristics of the participants.

The second category is based on the area of **teaching and learning**, defined in the framework as the management and organisation of the use of digital technologies during teaching and learning processes. This dimension will enable an analysis of the methodological strategies implemented by professionals, the forms of support provided to young people, and the promotion of collaborative or self-directed learning activities.

The third category relates to the area of **assessment and feedback**, which

addresses the use of digital technologies to support the monitoring of learning, the collection of evidence and the provision of feedback to participants. Within the framework of

this research, the focus will not be on the learning outcomes achieved by young people, but rather on the practices developed by professionals to monitor training processes, track progress and guide decision-making.

Finally, this dimension incorporates the area of **student empowerment**, centred on the potential of digital technologies to foster autonomy, inclusion, personalisation and active participation in learning processes. The analysis will enable us to identify how training initiatives incorporate strategies to enhance accessibility and promote meaningful participation by young people in their own learning pathways.

Table 2. Example of an analysis grid for the professional dimension

DigCompEdu Area	Observable aspects
Digital content	Selection of resources, adaptation of materials, creation of resources
Teaching and learning	Methodological strategies, support, collaborative learning, autonomy
Assessment and feedback	Follow-up, feedback, monitoring of learning
Empowerment of participants	Inclusion, accessibility, personalisation, active participation

DigCompOrg indicators

This third dimension focuses on the organisational context in which training takes place. To this end, the proposal draws on DigCompOrg and, specifically, is based on the areas operationalised through the SELFIE tool.

As argued previously, the aim of the research is not to assess the level of digital maturity of the centres nor to carry out an overall evaluation of their digital transformation. SELFIE will be used as a reference to identify those organisational elements that may influence the planning, development and sustainability of actions aimed at strengthening young people's digital competences in E2Os.

Based on this objective, the organisational dimension focuses on those areas that have a more direct relationship with the institutional capacity of E2Os to maintain and coordinate this type of initiative. The first category of analysis relates to **strategic planning**, which will provide insight into the institutional decisions, priorities and guidelines that define the place digital skills occupy within the centre's projects and activities. This analysis will enable us to assess whether the development of digital skills constitutes an explicit line of action, how it is integrated into institutional planning, and to what extent the actions undertaken respond to an organised strategy rather than one-off or isolated initiatives.

The second category relates to **collaboration**, a dimension that refers to the coordination and joint working mechanisms involved in the design, implementation and monitoring of activities. In this area, the dynamics of collaboration between professionals, the exchange of resources and

experiences, as well as the relationships established with external stakeholders, partner organisations, companies or other bodies that may contribute to the development of young people’s digital skills.

The third category relates to the **professional development** and capacity-building of staff involved in the design, implementation and monitoring of initiatives for the development of digital skills. This dimension enables an analysis of how E2Os facilitate the updating of knowledge, the acquisition of new skills and the continuous improvement of professional practices, through strategies aimed at identifying training needs, promoting internal and external training opportunities, providing resources for professional development and offering institutional support that contributes to the development of digital skills amongst professionals.

The fourth category focuses on **infrastructure and resources**, understood as the physical and technological conditions that enable the delivery of training activities. The analysis will enable the identification of the availability and suitability of devices, connectivity, digital platforms and other technological resources necessary for the implementation of the programmes, paying particular attention to the opportunities and limitations that these conditions present for the young participants.

Table 3. Example of an analysis grid for the organisational dimension

Organisational area (SELFIE)	Strategies and planning	Coordination and collaboration	Resources and infrastructure	Institutional
Strategic planning	Inclusion of digital skills in plans and projects; institutional ; ; planned	Coordination mechanisms for the planning; involvement of professionals in defining objectives	Resources allocated for the implementation of the actions	Allocation of responsibilities; institutional support for the implementation of the strategy

Collaboration and networks	Strategies to promote	Coordination between	Platforms or tools	Organisational organisational for
	the collaboration and professional partnerships	; exchange of experiences and resources; collaboration with companies, organisations and external stakeholders	used for collaborative work	collaboration and networking
Professional development	Identification of training needs; planning of training initiatives	Coordination for the development of training and professional development professional	Resources and tools for professional development	In-house and external training; career support; promotion of digital among the staff.
Infrastructure and resources	Planning of technological and digital resources	Coordination for the management and use of resources	Devices, connectivity, digital platforms, software, spaces and technological	Technical support and maintenance or update mechanisms

Validation of the proposal

In order to ensure the coherence, relevance and applicability of DigiScope-E2O, the proposal will undergo a validation process involving expert review. To this end, specialists in digital skills, educational and socio-occupational guidance, educational technology and support for vulnerable groups from the OrientaDig project will be involved; they will review the general structure of the instrument, the appropriateness of its dimensions and categories of analysis, as well as its alignment with the research objectives.

In addition, a pilot application of the assessment grids is planned, using a small set of documents and interviews from Second Chance Schools. This process will enable the identification of any potential interpretation difficulties, the adjustment of operational definitions and the verification of the

feasibility of the instrument for the systematic analysis of the information prior to its final implementation.

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Appendices

Interview template for professionals and programme managers involved in digital skills programmes at E2Os

Given the organisational diversity of E2Os and the involvement of different professionals and organisations in activities related to digital skills, this guide is designed to be an open and flexible tool. In order to make the most of the interview time and facilitate the collection of relevant information, certain sections have been assigned primarily to specific roles. This breakdown is intended as a guide and reflects the areas in which each participant typically has the most experience or knowledge. However, the interview may be adapted according to each person's background, responsibilities and level of involvement.

Section 1. Professional background (Both profiles)

Objective: to understand the participant's profile and their connection to the training activities.

1. What is your role within the Second Chance School?
2. What role do you play in the design, development or monitoring of activities related to digital skills?
3. How long have you been working on this type of programme?

Block 2. Design and planning of training activities (Both profiles)

Objective: to understand how digital initiatives are conceived and organised.

4. How important are digital skills within the Second Chance School's educational and socio-occupational programme?
 - Why do you consider it important to develop them?
 - What needs do they aim to address?
 - What role do they play in young people's pathways?
5. What objectives and content are incorporated into the activities aimed at developing digital skills?

- What factors are taken into account when defining these objectives and content?

6. How are the digital needs of the young participants identified?

7. Are there any guidelines, frameworks or documents to inform the planning of activities?

Other

- Who is involved in designing these initiatives?
- Are they reviewed or updated periodically?

Section 3. Implementation of the training (trainers/guidance counsellors)

Objective: to explore how these are carried out in practice.

8. How do they usually unfold the activities related to digital skills?

9. What digital resources and tools do they usually use?

10. What methodologies do you consider most suitable for develop these skills with young people?

11. Could you describe an activity or experiencethat do you consider to be representative?

12. How do the various professionals involved coordinate their efforts during the implementation of these initiatives?

Other

- Is the work carried out individually, in groups or a combination of both?
- Are real-life situations linked to everyday life or work used?

Section 4. Adaptation and support (trainers/advisers)

Objective: to understand how the diverse needs of participants are addressed.

12. What difficulties do young people usually encounter whilst carrying out these activities?
13. How do they adapt training activities to the different needs, levels or circumstances of the participants?
14. What strategies do they use to support young people throughout the learning process?

Other

- How are situations of demotivation or insecurity regarding the use of technology addressed?

Section 5. Assessment and monitoring (trainers/advisers)

Objective: to identify how learning and the development of skills are assessed.

16. How do you monitor young people's progress?
17. What indicators or evidence do they consider when assessing the development of digital skills?
18. Which digital skills do you think young people find easiest to develop?
And which ones do they find most difficult?

Block 6. Integration of digital training into E2O (managers)

Objective: to understand the role of digital competence initiatives within the centre's educational and socio-occupational strategy.

19. Are digital skills primarily developed through specific programmes, or are they integrated across the board into other training activities and processes?
20. How do these initiatives align with the organisation's overall objectives and educational strategy?

Other

- Are they part of institutional planning?

- Are there established lines of work?
 - Are they considered a priority?
 - How are they coordinated with other activities at the school?
21. What strategies or initiatives does the organisation implement to promote the development of digital skills amongst the guidance professionals at its school?
- In-house or external training.
 - Identification of training needs.
 - Opportunities for professionals to exchange ideas.
 - Support resources or tools.
 - Digital skills considered a priority for the team.